

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Analysis of mobility demand & transport offer for the pilot case

SPOKE 4 – Montagna Digitale e Sostenibile

DELIVERABLE D3.2 INTERFACE

RESEARCH MODULE 3 - *Proof of Concept for a shared and collective transport service for rural communities*

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is focused on the Demand Responsive Mobility models, and presents:

- the functioning of the DRM models and the collection of worldwide best practices;
- the results of the quantitative analysis of the demand for mobility and public transport supply, in order to identify the needs in the study area.

The analysis, based on established quantitative methods, will be integrated with a qualitative assessment (in-depth interviews, focus groups and on-site observations) to be carried out in the next period.

This report presents the preliminary findings on the study areas and will provide the baseline for the proposition of a DRM specific model for the pilots, and the development of a PoC.

A) Adaptive and flexible mobility models in rural areas: DRTS

The Demand Responsive Transport Services (DRTS) (also known as Demand Responsive Services or on-demand services) are public transport services that aim to provide flexible, efficient and convenient transportation or delivery options tailored to individual needs. They are activated only when requested by users and whose vehicles change routes according to a particular transport demand rather than using fixed routes or schedules. Such vehicles usually pick up and drop off passengers at specific locations based on passenger needs and may include cabs, buses, or other vehicles.

DRTS services can:

- replace unprofitable traditional public transport services, in smaller cities or in rural and mountain areas with low populations and high spatial dispersion;
- complement traditional public transport services by facilitating access (first and last mile connections);
- serve new user segments that do not use public transport, offering greater flexibility and greater quality;
- increase the overall efficiency of public transport systems.

They are public services that can be placed between collective cab services and traditional public transport:

- as they are flexible as collective cabs (which do not have fixed rides or timetables, but adapt to demand), offered with increased capacity vehicles (generally minimum 9 seats) and with the need to optimize trips to increase the number of passengers (higher load factor);
- as traditional public transport services, they are aimed at meeting social needs and not commercial and economic ones.

So, where a traditional public transport service is financially unsustainable because it is potentially affected by low and rarefied demand, DRTS services can be a valid alternative, offering a service that is closer to the user needs (personalization, duration and comfort of travel, ...).

DRTS are mainly characterized as services:

- "user-oriented," as they adapt routes, schedules, and frequency to the demand needs;
- accessible, through the use of specific platforms that allow to: book trips, optimize routes to increase load factor, offer cashless payment systems, integrate the service with other mobility;
- systems (MaaS), synchronize on-demand mobility with traditional line systems;
- adaptable, depending on the area or type of users to be served.

The elements that can condition the development of DRTS services can be summarized as follows:

- availability of new technologies (ITS, ICT, Internet, smartphones, ...);
- depopulation of rural areas and settlement sprawl in urban centres that makes complex trips within the cities;
- attitude of the population toward sharing mobility;
- increased environmental and health awareness.

Their potential benefits lie in the three pillars of sustainability:

- social sustainability: inclusion, reduced congestion;
 - environmental sustainability: reduction of pollutant emissions and noise;
-

- economic sustainability: increased efficiency of local public transport in areas of weak demand.

Critical issues related to the deployment of DRTS are related to:

- the digital divide, which may undermine the diffusion of new technologies to serve next-generation DRTS;
- the risk of being in conflict with local public transport if DRTS is not designed as complement.

Demand Responsive Transport (DRT) Models

For a clear view of possible organizational models for DRTs, the ENEA document "Demand Responsive Transport Services: Towards the Flexible Mobility Agency"¹ proposes a classification of services with an increasing level of flexibility on routes and transit times.

Legend	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Predefined stop, always served, with scheduling □ Predefined stop, with scheduling, served only on request ○ Predefined stop, without scheduling, served only on request ⬆ Virtual stop stop identified by an address or, for example, by the name of a place/building 	
	<p>Extension of a traditional service, with predefined route and schedule</p>	<p>Stops and route are known. Some extension stops can be served on demand. The feasibility of such a service is limited because the extension route may lead to severe delays on the non-demand route</p>
	<p>Detour of a scheduled service along predefined routes</p>	<p>Detour leads to increased direct route times, so it is important to seek the right balance between detour and default route. Users must be informed in relation to delay margins on fixed service stops</p>
	<p>Predefined stops in an area, but served only on demand</p>	<p>Fixed or variable routes. The structure of the service is closely related to the stops to be served. Service feasible with introduction of limitations on possible routes or in case of user flexibility on times and routes</p>
	<p>Virtual stops in an area</p>	<p>Represents the service with the greatest flexibility, where stops and routes can vary freely within a given area</p>
	<p>Stand-alone or integrated</p>	<p>A DRT can be designed as: stand-alone service, with no spatial or temporal relationship with traditional public transport services</p>

¹ Ambrosino G., Nelson J.D., Romanazzo M. (2003), "Demand Responsive Transport Services Towards the Flexible Mobility Agency", ENEA

		integrated service with traditional public transport services, both road and rail
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Table 1. Demand Responsive Transport Services (Source: ENEA, 2003)

DRT good practices

Here are 18 good practices of Demand-Responsive Transport (DRT) services, some of which have been implemented in mountainous or rural areas with a high dispersion of population. These practices are described by highlighting their primary objectives, key operational features, and the specific locations where they have been implemented.

MOBITALY	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mobitaly
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptive and flexible group transport services ("bubble-bus"). Door-to-door transport (e.g., home-to-work, home-to-school, home-to-hospital)
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automatically generated timetables, routes and stops based on mobility demand data Demand can be static (e.g., surveys) or dynamic (e.g., reservation app) Integrated with existing LPT and other modes of transport (e.g., carpooling) Transport performed by any means for passenger transport (e.g., bus, minibus, cab, NCC) Safe, homogeneous users, always travel with who you know, seats only, unidirectional and separated by high backs. Limitation of contact between passengers and vertical drop-down ventilation system and frequent air exchange
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Italy

MOEVES	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moeves, DRT bus in Cuneo
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time and door-to-door transport services for the city and hamlets

How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reservation via App/web/call-center in real time or for other days Reservation by the following methods: as early as possible (by setting the desired departure or arrival time), or by indicating only the time you wish to arrive at your destination Discounted fares for TPL season ticket holders Dedicated and specially trained driver Payment directly on board or via App. If holding public transport BIP cards, payment can be made with transport credit
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Italy, city of Cuneo and its hamlets

WIIIIK	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wiiilik: DRT in the Briançon area
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-demand transport services
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An annual subscription of 18€ that allows you to benefit from discounts on travel It is managed by the Wiiilik App that allows to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Book your trip Follow the waiting vehicle in real time Register your credit card Follow your children's journey and receive a message at their destination Parents interface: a "parents" interface allows you to follow younger children on their journey from departure to arrival, ensuring a safe transfer.
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> France, in the Briançon-Serre Chevalier, Montgenevre and Clarée Valley area

SOPOTNIKI	

Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sopotniki
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demand-responsive transport service with high social inclusion value to prevent the state of isolation and loneliness of elderly people from small remote villages due to lack of transport means or poor traffic connections
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volunteer drivers (retired or unemployed) • Small vehicles, provided by municipalities (often cars from municipal fleets) • High capillarity and ductility, for a country with high population dispersion • Management through an APP • Getting around becomes easy and pleasant (friendships are established with drivers)
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slovenia

BUMMELBUS

Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bummelbus
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demand-responsive transport services with vocational rehabilitation goals • It is a complementary service to public and private transport
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drivers are trained ad hoc and selected from long-term unemployed people • Efficiently groups customers traveling in the same area in order to reduce road congestion and have an ecological footprint • Key success factors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding of a mobility service by the Ministry of Labor - Extension of the service toward schoolchildren for their after-school activities
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Luxembourg

VILLAGE BUS

Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> «Village Bus» in Kolsillre
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demand-responsive transport (DRT) services in "self-management" Autonomous organization of public transport by village residents
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The service is through the use of minibuses purchased/rented by municipalities Undefined routes and schedules Use of a web portal for managing travel requests Free service The bus is parked in the village and in most cases heads to Ange, a larger town located 45 km away It is possible to request stops at specific points and set times You can pick up/drop off people along the way
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sweden, in Kolsillre

QUIBUS	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quibus
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexible and safe real-time evening Demand-responsive transport services. Free float service using traditional LPT stops
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offered in real time with reservation exclusively on APP that can be made up to one week before the trip When booking, the QUIBUS platform checks schedules, bus and seat availability and immediately provides information on waiting time, departure stop and bus number It is a secure service (an important feature due to the hours of operation) because all users must

	<p>register on the App and are identified by the driver on each journey</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The buses belong to the company, the drivers do not. This allows the quality of service to be kept under control (they are always the same, they are properly trained) Passengers must have a city ticket/subscription or can pay by credit card through the QUIBUS App
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Italy, Padova

KOMBIBUS	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> kombiBUS Gruppe
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Freight transport services with TLP vehicles
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of a LPT vehicle that upon request (telephone reservation) can also transport goods (food, mail, luggage, ...) <p>Activation of the service required an amendment to the Land Law, which did not provide for the possibility of transporting freight and passengers on the same vehicle.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Routes, stops, vehicles, and schedules of the passenger service are also those of the freight service Depending on the goods to be transported, existing luggage space or a trailer is used
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Germany, Land Brandenburg

COLLABORATIVE MOBILITY IN EPIRO	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative mobility in Epirus. Co-operation with the Hellenic Postal Service, transportation companies, logistics companies, and

	municipalities
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collective mobility services based on coordination between public LPT and courier services in rural areas
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordination between traditional TPL and postal courier and freight services to provide better service in rural, isolated and dispersed areas, including for student mobility Municipalities not served or poorly served by LPT benefit from some additional lines, implemented through the delivery of parcels and postal products The operating cost is covered by revenues from postal services, parcel delivery, product deliveries
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greece

ZEELO + BUSRAPIDO	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zeelo, British bus sharing company Busrapido, Roman bus booking startup (technology provider)
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dedicated services for companies to safely transport commuters by bus Safe buses that respect (social) safety distances
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mobile application for booking your own rides and being able to track bus location in real time, with routes optimized to ensure that pick-up and collection points are as convenient as possible Routing, timing, and pick-up points are fully flexible, allowing both scheduled and ad hoc trips to be managed Limited number of passengers on board "selected" through the booking site (and app) to ensure social distancing. The booking site (and app) ensures that safe distances are respected by using smart booking technology that monitors the number of people on board Thorough cleaning of the vehicle every day and surfaces disinfected after each trip Presence of hand sanitizer on board for all passengers Drivers provided with personal protective equipment (PPE) and a contact tracking tool Service activated in 24 hours (Get up and running in 24 hours)
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Italy (a service already present in the UK and South Africa)

BUSFORFUN (in partnership with local transport companies)	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Busforfun (technology provider), Venetian-Apulian company that offers a platform for booking buses • Partnerships with local transport companies throughout Ital
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Company shuttle service for safe transport of commuters by bus • Safe buses that respect (social) safety distances
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of perfectly sanitized rental vehicles of transport companies • Temperature control of passengers before boarding and the provision of protective equipment (presence on board of gloves and mask, sanitizing gel) • Reservation technologies, data analysis, and transport organization to safely manage the seat distribution of each individual vehicle
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italy

THE KINGS FERRY	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Kings Ferry, bus rental company
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe return to work for your staff • Sanitized and safe buses

How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily cleaning of vehicles and regular disinfection with antiviral products of all high contact areas • Minimizing driver-passenger interaction • Drivers provided with personal protective equipment • Visual reminders regarding social distancing on board • Scheduled bus occupancy (passengers should first occupy the rear seats and leave the vehicle in reverse order to avoid passing seated passengers) • Reduction of maximum passenger capacity: use of designated seats only in accordance with social spacing rules. Unavailable seats will be clearly indicated • Technology that offers companies the ability to manage and monitor the number of passengers by reservation and has contact tracking capabilities
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • United Kingdom

SWAT MOBILITY + TOYOTA MOBILITY FOUNDATION

Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Swat Mobility, Singapore-based company specializing in "Smart transport solutions" (technology provider) • Toyota Mobility Foundation
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe (and free) transportation for health workers at the General Hospital in Manila, Philippines. Service for a thousand people • Sanitized and safe buses
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Just in Time service for calculating routes that fit and are automatically generated based on who has booked a ride • Trip booking via app up to 30 minutes before departure • Automatic seat assignment based on social spacing measures and halved vehicle capacity for this purpose • Vehicles equipped with air purification devices and products to sanitize passengers. Vehicles sanitized frequently, and seat covers changed periodically

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle tracking and real time display of bus location
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manila, Bangkok e Jakarta

LEAP TRANSIT	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start-up in the transport sector
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Premium commuter transportation • Fixed price \$6 per trip
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services only during peak hours, every 15-20 minutes • 27 seats • Few stops, fast services • Extra-luxury interiors equipped like offices (e.g., counters to rest your desktop, wifi, usb and electrical outlets) • Premium amenities (e.g., concierge, minibar with drinks and snacks that can be ordered pre-trip) • Started in 2015 and was closed shortly after because it did not comply with regulation for LPT (e.g., Municipality authorization, handicapped accessibility) but also for low ridership (wrong target, perceived as unfair)
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • San Francisco

OFFICE ON WHEELS	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2018: Staf Cars (bus rental company) • 2016: feasibility project sponsored by the Flemish government with numerous partners (e.g., Professional Association of Bus and Coach Operators, Flemish Institute for Mobility, Proxima (telephony), Van Hool (bus manufacturer))
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Premium commuter transportation
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily service • 21 places • Online booking service • Interiors equipped as offices (e.g. counters to support the desktop, wifi, USB and electrical outlets) • Premium services (e.g. printer, coffee machine, fridge, toilets) • Identification of dedicated routes and lanes to speed up the journey • When the bus is stopped it is used to give lessons on board • Business model and conditions for service sustainability • Different riders since 2016 (e.g. Ghent, Antwerp)
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From/To Liegi

PRONTOBUS EXTRA	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ProntoBus Extra
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DRT bus service created to facilitate mobility in the rural area and unserved places
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telephone booking service: possibility of booking the desired ride the day before the trip or the day of the trip itself • Reservations received on the same day of the trip will be accepted subject to availability. • Reservation service available every weekday and Saturday • The fees are the same as in the suburban network and change according to the number of areas

	crossed
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Italy, Parma

ALLO NUIT	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allo Nuit
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DRT evening and night public transport service, given in sub-concession to a group of Taxi Drivers/Night Riders in Aosta
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The service can be requested from 9 p.m. to 5:30 a.m. No reservation is required. The service will be provided without the use of telephone switchboard. The user will have to call the driver directly Fixed cost ticket, different costs per urban or suburban network Users can buy the ticket on board or at sales points
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Italy, Aosta

RING A LINK	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ring a link
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community mobility services in rural area
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online booking service Fixed cost ticket: €3.00 for one-way travel for adults, €2.00 for children under 16, children under 5 travel free The service is available every day and on a regular basis with DRT and scheduled services Door-to-door transport
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ireland, Kilkenny

TRANSPORT A PEDIDO	
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport a pedido
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community mobility services in rural area • Innovative, flexible, integrating solution that reduce the ecological footprint
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telephone booking service • The user must call the Reservation Center by phone before 3 p.m. the day before the trip • Ticket price varies. Users can buy the ticket on board, fares vary between €1.20 and €8.00 depending on the origin/destination distance of the service • Daily service • Trips have a fixed origin and destination
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portugal

B) Analysis of mobility demand and supply in the Valle d'Aosta

Framework of the public transport sector in the Valle d'Aosta region

The Aosta Valley Region constitutes a territorial unit where an integrated public transport system is implemented, involving bus services coordinated with rail transportation and other modes of public transport. This territorial unit is referred to as a traffic basin (Article 5 L.R. 29/97). The Valle d'Aosta area is divided into 6 sub-basins, of which one (called 'Fondo Valle') extends along the entire Aosta-Ivrea ridge, while 5 are identifiable by area boundaries and group together several municipalities: Upper Valley (13 municipalities), Aosta and Belt (9 municipalities), Central Valley (18 municipalities), Middle Valley (12 municipalities), Lower Valley (22 municipalities).

In order to identify mobility needs and the demand for bus public transportation, the Region approves and implements a traffic basin plan. The traffic basin plan is prepared by the competent regional body responsible for transportation, in consultation with the bus transport concessionaires and the most representative trade unions and includes: a) the structure and organization of the local public transport system in the regional territory; b) the indication of minimum services that are qualitatively and quantitatively sufficient to meet the mobility demand of users, with costs borne by the regional budget, and the methods by which they must be provided; c) the identification of types and methods of developing complementary services; d) the territorial division into sub-basins, along with a description of their number and characteristics; e) the maximum distances allowed for all lines within the sub-basin, eligible for service contract agreements; f) coordination of bus services with other modes of transportation and cable installations for local public transportation purposes; g) areas and intermodal exchange parking facilities to be enhanced and h) guidelines for tariff policy (Article 6 L.R. 29/97).

The Region therefore carries out programming and planning activities, as well as managing procedures for selecting the service concessionaire and concluding the relevant contract.

The main regulatory references for public transport in Valle d'Aosta are:

- the Regional Law no. 29 of 1 September 1997 (Rules on public line transport service) which regulates collective public transport services for persons and goods of regional and local interest carried out, normally, on a continuous or periodic basis, with pre-established routes, timetables, frequency and fares and undifferentiated supply. The Law assigns to the Region the planning and coordination of public transport exercised through the preparation of a regional transport and communication plan (Art. 2). Furthermore, the Region (Article 13-bis) promotes the development of intramodality in the local public transport services;
- the Regional Law no. 22 of 25 November 2016 (Provisions for a modern railway and an efficient integrated public transport system) in which the improvement of the railway service is considered indispensable and urgent due to its value in relation to local mobility, tourist use and environmental quality.

In the municipalities of the region where the regional public transport service is lacking or inadequate, the municipalities or Unités des Communes, by delegation of the municipalities, organise and manage local public transport and provide for the economic coverage of the entire cost of the services organised and managed (Art. 3 L.R. 29/97). the full cost of the services organised and managed (Article 3 of Regional Law 29/97). In the villages of the Aosta Municipality with less than 500 inhabitants and in the municipalities of the Region where the regional public transport service is lacking or inadequate, the Municipalities or the Unités des Communes, by delegation of the municipalities, organise and manage

local public transport and provide for the economic coverage of the entire cost of the services organised and managed (Art. 3 L.R. 29/97).

The main regional planning tool is represented by the Regional Transport and Communication Plan, which must be adopted by the Region in coherence with the contents of the territorial and landscape plan of Valle d'Aosta. On 16 April 2019, the draft of the new Plan was presented².

The Plan is articulated by crossing three levels of interaction transport-territory with infrastructure/new technology systems, mobility services and sectoral policies, against which three macro-objectives of the PRT 2020- 2030:

- improving internal mobility with a view to sustainable development (economic, social and environmental);
- strengthen connections with neighboring regions in support of the development of the regional tourism system;
- improve the integration of the Aosta Valley in the network of European corridors and the main national passenger and freight traffic routes.

In addition to outlining the current situation, the plan also defines guidelines for improvement by dedicating a section to DRT services for those municipalities with the greatest depopulation and ageing, which are therefore identified as “weak demand lines”. The plan identifies territories with weak demand for which it wants to guarantee territorial continuity through public transport services with flexible routes and/or timetables. These services, by stopping at equipped nodes, make it possible to intercept the offer of the enhanced regional rail and car carrier network, so as to guarantee greater overall accessibility in destination to the main poles of regional interest (Figure 1). It is also suggesting to utilise the COMBI type of Demand-Responsive Transport (DRT) service, when required, for transporting individuals and small deliveries of essential goods (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Municipalities with greater depopulation and aging where the use of DRT services is envisaged (extracted from the Regional Transport Plan, 2021).

Figure 2. Weak demand lines where the use of Demand Responsive Transport services is envisaged COMBI (extracted from the Regional Transport Plan, 2021).

For the analysis of transport supply and demand at regional level, the reference is the Regional Transport Plan, which presents the most recent and official data, while identifying strategies for improvement.

² https://www.regione.vda.it/territorio/allegati/progetti_via_2377_Piano.pdf.

In the Valle d'Aosta region three main transport operators were identified and classified in this work according to the type of service offered³:

- SAVDA: “Società Autolinee Valle d'Aosta” is a major bus operator in the region, providing regular bus services that connect various towns and villages within Valle d'Aosta, as well as offering connections to neighboring regions.
- VITA: “Valdostana impresa trasporti automobilistici” manages local public transport services in Valle d'Aosta, interregional tourism lines and private transfers from major airports and railway stations to/from Valle d'Aosta.
- Trenitalia: the national railway operator, Trenitalia, provides train services within the Valle d'Aosta region along the 'Aosta - Pont-Saint-Martin' railway line (which then continues outside the Aosta Valley towards Ivrea, Chivasso and Turin).

The Unitès de Communes “Grand Paradis” and “Mont Cervin”

Valle d'Aosta region is divided in nine *Unité des communes*, two of them have been selected as study areas: the territory of Gran-Paradis which includes the municipalities of Arvier, Aise, Aymavilles, Cogne, Introd, Rhêmes-Notre-Dame, Rhêmes-Saint-Georges, Saint-Nicolas, Saint-Pierre, Sarre, Valgrisenche, Valsavarenche, Villeneuve and the territory of Mont-Cervin which includes the municipalities of Antey-Saint-André, Chambave, Chamois, Châtillon, La Magdeleine, Pontey, Saint-Denis, Saint-Vincent, Torgnon. Aosta is the provincial capital and Gran-Paradis is the unité with the highest number of municipalities (n = 13).

The unité Mont Cervin counts 16,028 residents (12.92%) and the unité Grand Paradis 15,432 residents (12.44%) (Source: the Economic and Social Observatory - Autonomous Region of Valle d'Aosta and ISTAT data, 2021). The populations residing in the pilot areas is respectively at the third and the fourth place in term of percentage incidence of population, following the provincial capital (27.1% of total regional population) and the unité Mont Emilius (22,513 residents, 18% of regional total).

Grand-Paradis and Mont-Cervin are the units where most of the foreign population resides, after the city of Aosta units. Both unites are characterized by municipalities located predominantly in the mid-mountain or mid-valley.

The area of Gran-Paradis covers about 826 square kilometres and the main centre is Sarre, the most populated municipality in the region after the capital. The third most populated municipality in the region is Châtillon in Mont-Cervin followed by the neighboring Saint-Vincent, a famous tourism destination.

Valle d'Aosta Regional council is the main public administration organization followed by the Unité des communes and the municipalities. The main purpose of the Unité is to foster the development of the valleys while safeguarding the local environmental and cultural heritage.

The main three hospitals are in Aosta, while both Unité have eight main social health facilities. There are two micro-communities in Pontey and Valtournenche for elderly people and people with disabilities.

³ In addition, there is also the Skyway Monte Bianco, a cable car operator that offers transportation services to access the Mont Blanc massif, providing scenic views and access to mountainous areas.

Preschools, primary schools, and secondary schools are spread throughout the territory. Mont-Cervin and Grand-Paradis are the units with the largest number of pre-schools and primary schools after Aosta and Mont-Emilius.

The GAL (Gruppo d'Azione Locale) Valle d'Aosta also act at the local level and is a recognised non-profit association under private law, constituted with the priority aim of coordinating and implementing the Local Development Strategy (SSL) "Une Vallée d'Aoste à soutenir et découvrir en réseau", a project for the valorisation of the territory centred on sustainable tourism understood as responsible tourism that brings positive repercussions on the territory in environmental, employment and cultural terms. This is the only one active on the regional territory and is composed by 83 public and private members representing the socio-economic reality. The GAL Valle d'Aosta's geographical area of reference covers almost the entire territory of the Autonomous Region of Valle d'Aosta, comprising 73 of the 74 municipalities. The municipality of Aosta is excluded, since is not eligible for funding as it is classified as an urban and peri-urban area.

Each municipality has his own Pro Loco: local associations created with the aim of promoting and developing the area. Other associations are mainly related to sport activities (fishing, hunting, skiing, trekking), religious issues, arts and traditions, and environmental protection such as firefighter's volunteers, civil protection, and Grand-Paradis Mountain community rescue volunteers.

The most productive industry is in the hydroelectric power plants. Today, the industries are concentrated in the lower valley and are small to medium-sized enterprises. It is very active in the food, textile, construction, mechanical, wood and paper sectors. Mont-Cervin is the third area by number of companies, even though the economy of the Unité is mainly based on tourism sector and tourist facilities (hotel, B&Bs, restaurants).

The main public transport operator is SVAP S.r.l.-Società Valdostana Autoservizi Pubblici ensuring the public bus transport service in the Aosta sub-basin with a fleet of over 63 buses, tailored to the various routes in the Aosta region. For Urban and Suburban Lines there is also V.I.T.A. S.p.A. with an offer of cars, minibuses, and buses from 4 to 91 seats. Some municipalities are connected by the company ARRIVA Italia which operates also at suburban level connecting with Lombardy region, in particular the city of Milan with the main touristic places of Aosta valley.

Figure 3. Study areas selected for accessibility analysis.

Selection of the main Origins and Destinations in the Unitès de Communes according to the cluster analysis

The destinations of the journeys correspond to the municipalities with the highest concentration of services (such as social welfare and hospital services, schools) and other mobility generators (micro-enterprises and SMEs) (clusters 5 and 6 of the cluster analysis on the “mobility generators” included in the D3.1). The following table (Table 2) lists the municipalities chosen as destinations for the two study areas where it was considered appropriate to also consider the two municipalities of Aosta and Verres, albeit outside the study area, due to their proximity to the two *Unitès de Communes* and since they are among the main generators of mobility for the regional context.

Unitès de Communes	Destinations
Grand Paradis	Aosta (out of area)
Mont Cervin	Saint Vincent, Valtournenche, Chatillon, Verrès (out of area)

Table 2. Destinations of the journeys for the two study areas: Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and Unitès de Communes Mont Cervin.

Origins are identified by looking at the municipalities where there are low values of services offered and enterprises (clusters 1 and 2 of the cluster analysis on the “mobility generators” included in the D3.1 and represented Figure 4), high values of commuters, population and tourists (clusters 2, 4 and 6 of the cluster analysis on the “mobility demand” included in the D3.1 and represented in Figure 5) and a certain degree of vulnerability due to the presence of many elderly, few young people, low population density and a negative demographic trend which indicates depopulation

(clusters 2, 4, 5 and 6 of the cluster analysis on the “vulnerability” included in the D3.1 and represented in Figure 6) (see Table 3 for the selection).

Figure 4. Mobility generators – cluster analysis: focus on the Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and Mont Cervin.

Figure 5. Mobility demand – cluster analysis: focus on the Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and Mont Cervin.

Figure 6. Vulnerability – cluster analysis: focus on the Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and Mont Cervin.

Unitès de Communes	Origins	Mobility generators (clusters 1 and 2)	Mobility demand (clusters 2, 4 and 6)	Mobility Vulnerability (clusters 2, 4, 5 and 6)
Grand Paradis	Arvier	1	2	2
	Avise	1	2	5
	Aymavilles	2		2
	Cogne			5
	Introd	2	2	2
	Rhêmes-Notre- Dame	1		6
	Rhêmes-Saint-Georges	1	2	5
	Saint-Nicolas	1	2	2
	Saint-Pierre			
	Sarre			6
	Valgrisenche	1		4
	Valsavarenche	1		5

	Villeneuve	1		
Mont Cervin	Antey-Saint-André	2	2	5
	Chambave	1	2	5
	Chamois	1		4
	Châtillon		6	5
	La Magdeleine	1		2
	Pontey	2	2	
	Saint-Denis	1	2	
	Saint-Vincent	1	6	
	Torgnon	1		2
	Valtournenche		4	
Verrayes	1		2	

Table 3. Selection of the Origins of the Journeys for the two study areas: Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and Unitès de Communes Mont Cervin.

Selected as Origins for the present study are those municipalities that fall into 2 or 3 of the categories as presented in Table 4.

Unitès de Communes	Origins
Grand Paradis	Arvier, Avise, Aymavilles, Introd, Rhêmes-Notre- Dame, Rhêmes-Saint-Georges, Saint-Nicolas, Valgrisenche, Valsavarenche
Mont Cervin	Antey-Saint-André, Chambave, Chamois, Châtillon, La Magdeleine, Pontey, Saint-Denis, Saint-Vincent, Torgnon, Verrayes

Table 4. Origins of the journeys for the two study areas: Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and Unitès de Communes Mont Cervin.

Figure 7. Representation of potential OD relationships identified for the calculation of accessibility in the two study areas: Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and Mont Cervin.

In order to validate the results obtained from the cluster analysis with respect to the identification of Origins and Destinations and also to frame mobility in the two study areas, an analysis of the Istat commuting matrices (for work and study reasons) presented in the following section was carried out.

Mobility demand analysis: commuting data for the Unitès de Communes

Commuting data from the latest ISTAT Census (2011) were processed in order to examine the framework of commuting habits and behavior in the municipalities of the two Unitès de Communes. The data under examination, although not very recent, were used to highlight macro phenomena related to commuting that, in principle, may not have changed so much over the years. For the analysis the municipalities of Gran Paradis and Mont Cervin were selected, and for these the daily outgoing trips (origin non-coincident with destination of trip) were investigated. Following the main results.

Figure 8. Map of the lines of desire from each of the municipalities in the Gran Paradis (% values compared to the total of the originated displacements).

Figure 9. Map of the lines of desire from each of the municipalities in the Gran Paradis (absolute values).

Figure 10. Map of the lines of desire from each of the municipalities in the Mont-Cervin (% values compared to the total of the originated displacements).

Figure 11. Map of the lines of desire from each of the municipalities in the Mont Cervin (absolute values).

The main origins deduced from the cluster analysis and reported in the previous paragraph are confirmed, with the exception of Cogne, which has enough commuters originated from within the relevant origins considered for the accessibility analysis.

Reasons for trips

The Mont Cervin municipalities generate more than twice trips compared with Gran Paradis, while for both areas the percentage of trip for study is around 20%.

In Gran Paradis area the municipality with the highest number of trips per day is Aymavilles, while Remes-Notre-Dame is the one with the highest percentage of trips for study (44%).

With reference to Mont Cervin area Chatillon and Saint-Vincent are the municipality that generates the highest number of trips toward other municipalities. Chamois registers more than 60% of trips for study.

Figure 12. Trips per reasons in Mont Cervin and Gran Paradis area (absolute numbers and %).

Figure 13. Trips per reasons in Gran Paradis area (absolute numbers and %).

Figure 14. Trips per reasons in Mont Cervin area (absolute numbers and %).

Modes of transport

For both areas of analysis, the private car is the most frequently used mean of transport, with about 80%, followed by the bus (urban + extra urban) with 10%. The train share stands at 5% for Mont Cervin and 3% for Gran Paradis.

Rhemes-Notre-Dame e Cogne are the municipalities with the higher share of use of bus.

Figure 15. Trips per modes of transport in Mont Cervin and Gran Paradis area (absolute numbers and %).

Figure 16. Trips per modes of transport in Gran Paradis area (absolute numbers and %).

Figure 17. Trips per modes of transport in Mont Cervin area (absolute numbers and %).

Departure time

The majority of journeys in both valleys is made by leaving home between 7:15 and 8:14 a.m. By 8:14 a.m. more than 80% of the trips begins. For the municipalities of Valgrisenche and Cogne about 70% of journeys departs by 7.15 a.m.

Figure 18. Trips per departure time in Mont Cervin and Gran Paradis area (absolute numbers and %).

Figure 19. Trips per departure time in Gran Paradis area (absolute numbers and %).

Figure 20. Trips per departure time in Mont Cervin Paradis area (absolute numbers and %).

Travel time

With regard to travel times, it is noted that they are mostly between 16 and 30 minutes, in Mont Cervin area at around 40%, in Gran Paradis area at around 50%.

The municipalities of Rhemes-Notre-Dame, Valsavarenche, Valgrisenche and Cogne have the highest percentage of trips between 31 and 60 minutes.

Figure 21. Trips per travel time in Mont Cervin and Gran Paradis area (absolute numbers and %).

Figure 22. Trips per travel time in Gran Paradis area (absolute numbers and %)

Figure 23. Trips per travel time in Mont Cervin area (absolute numbers and %).

Destinations

With reference to the analysis of the main destinations for trips originating in all the municipalities of the two valleys, it can be seen that the main polarities that emerged from the cluster analysis are also mostly confirmed by 2011 Istat data, even though with some slight variations (Table 5): Aosta municipality as main destination of Gran Paradis area, and the municipalities of Aosta, Chatillon, Saint-Vincent, Verrès, Valtournenche as main destinations of Mont Cervin area.

Grand Paradis (Destinations)			Mont Cervin (Destinations)		
Aosta	830	47%	Aosta	963	24%
Villeneuve	199	11%	Chatillon	683	17%
Saint-Pierre	108	6%	Saint-Vincent	574	14%
Saint-Christophe	90	5%	Verrès	268	7%
Sarre	50	3%	Valtournenche	160	4%
Courmayeur	44	2%	Saint-Christophe	127	3%
Morgex	41	2%	Verrayes	103	3%
Quart	36	2%	Quart	99	2%

Table 5. Main destinations for Grand Paradis and Mont Cervin areas.

The assessment framework

The methodology adopted to define the accessibility by private and public transport means within the two study areas considered: 1) Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis" and 2) Unitès de Communes Mont Cervin is articulated as follows:

1. definition of the Destinations (D) and Origins (O) of the journeys;
2. identification of the possible relationships between the O and D;
3. definition of the relevant accessibility indicators;
4. analysis of the accessibility indicators.

Definition of the Destinations (D) and Origins (O) of the journeys

Starting from the first definition of Destinations and Origins previously presented in Figure 7, Cogne has been added to the Origins due to its proven commuters' relation with Aosta (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Representation of the new potential OD relationships identified for the calculation of accessibility in the two study areas: Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and Mont Cervin.

Moreover, given the mountainous nature of the study areas, the population is scattered across various hamlets. As a result, there may be multiple Origins to consider, especially when certain hamlets hold significant importance. In this particular scenario, hamlets with a population exceeding 100 residents' population and situated more than 2 km away from the town hall have been considered. Indeed, for the Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis of Chambave (8 hamlets: Arlier with more than 100 inhabitants and more than 2 km away from the town hall), Châtillon (8 hamlets: Panorama and Ussel with more than 100 inhabitants and with more than 2 km away from the town hall), Saint-Vincent (16 hamlets: Moron and Cillian with more than 100 inhabitants and with more than 2 km away from the town hall) and Verrayes (21 hamlets: Champagne with more than 100 inhabitants and with more than 2 km away from the town hall)⁴. The approach varies when it comes to the Destinations, as we have only considered multiple locations for travels when the services are dispersed among different hamlets. This is specifically applicable to Valtournenche with 9 hamlets: Breuil-Cervinia and Maen with more than 100 inhabitants and with more than 2 km away from the town hall but only Breuil-Cervinia with a considerable concentration of services and enterprises.

The analysis of accessibility must necessarily refer to the places from which movements ideally originate or are destined and which coincide with a point located on the territory through geographical coordinates, that are called, in the literature "centroids". Centroids are defined for their Origins and Destinations to allow the determination of routes

⁴ The Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis has several hamlets with more than 100 inhabitants but none more than 2 km from the town hall: Avise (3 hamlets: Runaz with more than 100 inhabitants but less than 2 km away from the town hall), Introd (2 hamlets: Villes Dessous with more than 100 inhabitants but less than 2 km away from the town hall).

connecting different areas. Centroids in the literature can be access nodes to the area through transport networks (a car park, a public transport stop or a railway station), but also, in the case of tourist accessibility, places that offer opportunities or attractions to visitors (points of tourist interest, hotels or accommodation facilities). Ideally, they should be located in an area 'barycentric' for the area to ensure a certain equidistance to the notable points located there. In the present case, the Origins and Destinations exact points correspond to the town hall location or the main square (Table 6 and Table 7).

Unitès de Communes	Origins	Address
Grand Paradis	Arvier	Via Corrado Gex, 8
	Avisè	Località Capoluogo, 1
	Aymavilles	Frazione Chef Lieu, 1
	Cogne	Via Bourgeois, 56
	Introd	Località Plan D'Introd, 2
	Rhêmes-Notre-Dame	Località Bruil, 13
	Rhêmes-Saint-Georges	Località Vieux, 1
	Saint-Nicolas	Fraz, Frazione Fossaz Dessus, 1
	Valgrisenche	Loc. Capoluogo, 9
	Valsavarenche	Frazione, Località Degioz, 166
		Destinations
	Aosta	P.za Emile Chanoux, 1

Table 6. Origins and Destinations addresses for the Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis.

Unitès de Communes	Origins	Centroid Address	
Mont Cervin	Antey-Saint-André	Frazione Bourg, 1	
	Chambave	Piazza Orsieres, 1	
	Chambave-Arlier	Frazione Arlier	
	Chamois	Frazione Corgnolaz, 11	
	Châtillon	Via Emilio Chanoux, 11	
	Châtillon Panorama	Frazione Panorama	
	Châtillon Ussel	Frazione Ussel	
	La Magdeleine	Frazione Clou, 26	
	Pontey	Lassolaz	
	Saint-Denis	Frazione Saint Denis Capoluogo, 57	
	Saint-Vincent	Via A. Vuillerminaz, 7	
	Saint-Vincent Moron	Frazione Moron	
	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Frazione Cillian	
	Torgnon	Frazione Mongnod, 4	
	Verrayes	Località Capoluogo, 1	
	Verrayes Champagne	Frazione Champagne	
		Destinations	Address
		Aosta	P.za Emile Chanoux, 1
		Saint Vincent	Via A. Vuillerminaz, 7
		Valtournenche	Via della Chiesa, Paquier
	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	Frazione Breuil-Cervinia	
	Chatillon	Via Emilio Chanoux, 11	
	Verrès	Via Caduti della Libertà, 20	

Table 7. Origins and Destinations addresses for the Unitès de Communes Mont Cervin.

Identification of the possible relationships between the O and D

For the Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis, there are 10 Origins and 1 Destination, resulting in a total of 10 possible relationships. On the other hand, the Unitès de Communes Mont Cervin has 16 Origins and 6 Destinations, leading to a

total of 96 potential relationships (will be only considered relations from the Origins to the Destinations and not viceversa). However, it has been decided to exclude relationships where the municipality of Origin is the same as the municipality of Destination. The OD relations are therefore 10 for the Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis and 90 for the Unitès de Communes Mont Cervin.

ID	OD relation
GP1	Arvier- Aosta
GP2	Avise-Aosta
GP3	Aymavilles- Aosta
GP4	Cogne - Aosta
GP5	Introd- Aosta
GP6	Rhêmes-Notre-Dame- Aosta
GP7	Rhêmes-Saint-Georges- Aosta
GP8	Saint-Nicolas- Aosta
GP9	Valgrisenche- Aosta
GP10	Valsavarenche- Aosta

Table 8. The 10 OD relations for the accessibility analysis of the Unitès de Communes Grand Paradis.

ID	OD relation	ID	OD relation	ID	OD relation
MC1	Antey-Saint-André - Aosta	MC31	Châtillon Panorama - Saint Vincent	M61	Saint-Vincent - Chatillon
MC2	Antey-Saint-André - Saint Vincent	MC32	Châtillon Panorama - Valtournenche	M62	Saint-Vincent - Verrès
MC3	Antey-Saint-André - Valtournenche	MC33	Châtillon Panorama - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC63	Saint-Vincent Moron - Aosta
MC4	Antey-Saint-André - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC34	Châtillon Panorama - Verrès	MC64	Saint-Vincent Moron - Valtournenche
MC5	Antey-Saint-André - Chatillon	MC35	Châtillon Ussel - Aosta	MC65	Saint-Vincent Moron - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia
MC6	Antey-Saint-André - Verrès	MC36	Châtillon Ussel - Saint Vincent	MC66	Saint-Vincent Moron - Chatillon
MC7	Chambave - Aosta	MC37	Châtillon Ussel - Valtournenche	MC67	Saint-Vincent Moron - Verrès
MC8	Chambave - Saint Vincent	MC38	Châtillon Ussel - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC68	Saint-Vincent Cillian - Aosta
MC9	Chambave - Valtournenche	MC39	Châtillon Ussel - Verrès	MC69	Saint-Vincent Cillian - Valtournenche
MC10	Chambave - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC40	La Magdeleine - Aosta	MC70	Saint-Vincent Cillian - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia
MC11	Chambave - Chatillon	MC41	La Magdeleine - Saint Vincent	MC71	Saint-Vincent Cillian - Chatillon
MC12	Chambave - Verrès	MC42	La Magdeleine - Valtournenche	MC72	Saint-Vincent Cillian - Verrès
MC13	Chambave-Arlier - Aosta	MC43	La Magdeleine - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC73	Torgnon - Aosta
MC14	Chambave-Arlier - Saint Vincent	MC44	La Magdeleine - Chatillon	MC74	Torgnon - Saint Vincent
MC15	Chambave-Arlier - Valtournenche	MC45	La Magdeleine - Verrès	MC75	Torgnon - Valtournenche
MC16	Chambave-Arlier - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC46	Pontey - Aosta	MC76	Torgnon - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia
MC17	Chambave-Arlier - Chatillon	MC47	Pontey - Saint Vincent	MC77	Torgnon - Chatillon
MC18	Chambave-Arlier - Verrès	MC48	Pontey - Valtournenche	MC78	Torgnon - Verrès
MC19	Chamois - Aosta	MC49	Pontey - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC79	Verrayes - Aosta
MC20	Chamois - Saint Vincent	MC50	Pontey - Chatillon	MC80	Verrayes - Saint Vincent
MC21	Chamois - Valtournenche	MC51	Pontey - Verrès	MC81	Verrayes - Valtournenche
MC22	Chamois - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC52	Saint-Denis - Aosta	MC82	Verrayes - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia
MC23	Chamois - Chatillon	MC53	Saint-Denis - Saint Vincent	MC83	Verrayes - Chatillon

MC24	Chamois - Verrès	MC54	Saint-Denis - Valtournenche	MC84	Verrayes - Verrès
MC25	Châtillon - Aosta	MC55	Saint-Denis - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC85	Verrayes Champagne - Aosta
MC26	Châtillon - Saint Vincent	MC56	Saint-Denis - Chatillon	MC86	Verrayes Champagne - Saint Vincent
MC27	Châtillon - Valtournenche	MC57	Saint-Denis - Verrès	MC87	Verrayes Champagne - Valtournenche
MC28	Châtillon - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC58	Saint-Vincent - Aosta	MC88	Verrayes Champagne - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia
MC29	Châtillon - Verrès	MC59	Saint-Vincent - Valtournenche	MC89	Verrayes Champagne - Chatillon
MC30	Châtillon Panorama - Aosta	MC60	Saint-Vincent - Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	MC90	Verrayes Champagne - Verrès

Table 9. The 90 OD relations for the accessibility analysis of the Unitès de Communes Mont Cervin.

Definition of relevant accessibility indicators

In the case of travel by private motorised vehicle (car or motorbike), the route will coincide with a sequence of road sections, while the route taken by a public transport user will be linked to the route followed by the line (or combination of lines or different services, e.g. train+bus) used. It was therefore decided to subdivide the analysis by mode of transport, determining the most significant indicators according to the means considered. Specifically, in this case, the analysis using indicators was carried out on:

- private transport (4 indicators);
- public transport considering road, rail and combined rail-road (8 indicators).

Table 10 shows the 12 indicators selected and divided by transport mode.

Transport Mode	ID	Indicator	Unit of measure	Description
Private Transport (PrT)	PrT1	Travel time on the shortest path (off-peak hours) on a weekday	minutes	Travel time by car on the road route that minimises the time between the origin and destination of the journey
	PrT2	Travel time on the shortest path (peak hours) on a weekday	minutes	
	PrT3	Distance of the shortest path	km	Length, evaluated on the road network, of the route that minimises the time and the distance between the origin and destination of the journey
	PrT4	Toll	Yes/No	Describes whether the shortest path includes paid sections
Public Transport (PuT)	PuT1	Minimum travel time on the shortest path on a weekday	minutes	Time interval that minimises the connection time between the origin and destination of the journey during a weekday. A max. limit of 1km for walking trips and a max. limit of 30 min. including waiting time + walking time has been considered
	PuT2	Distance between the stops and the O / D	metres	Total walking distance between the public transport stop and the origin and the public transport stop and the destination.
	PuT3	Transhipments on the shortest path on a weekday	number	Number of connections with 0 transhipment (direct connections), with 1 transhipment, >1 transhipment, on a weekday
	PuT4	Connections with 0 transhipment on a weekday	number	
	PuT5	Connections with 1 transhipment on a weekday	number	
	PuT6	Connections with 2-3 transhipments on a weekday	number	
	PuT7	Connections in the 07-10 time slot taking the same time as the shortest path (+10 min) on a weekday	number	Number of connections available (regardless of the number of transhipments) during the peak hours on a weekday
	PuT8	Connections in the 10-13 time slot taking the same time as the shortest	number	Number of connections available (regardless of the number of transhipments) during the off-peak hours

	path (+10 min) on a weekday	on a weekday
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Table 10. Accessibility indicators, units of measurement and description, broken down by mode of transport for OD relations.

Google Map, the shortest path search engine, was used to perform the data collection.

The private transport mode queries were carried out on Wednesday 21/09/2023 with departure at 07:30 (peak-hours) and at 11:00 (off-peak hours). The public transport queries were carried out for Wednesday 14/06/2023. Frequency of PT service might be subject to change depending on the period (holiday, school year). Understanding these variations requires further queries for other days in the year, this is however not considered in the analysis performed for this report.

Moreover, the following criteria were used for public transport queries: a) selection of the route that minimises the travel time; b) maximum limit of 3 km for walking to the first stop and from the last stop to the final destination,

Analysis of accessibility by transport mode

The following section presents the results of accessibility analysis for private and public transport, followed by a short comparison of both transport modes.

Accessibility by private transport

Table 11 shows the accessibility indicators for private transport in Gran Paradis. Columns with indicators PrT1, PrT2 and PrT3 were coloured from green to red accordingly to the relative value of the cell for each column.

Relation ID	Origin	Destination	Travel time on the shortest path (off-peak hours) on a weekday [PrT1]	Travel time on the shortest path (peak hours) on a weekday [PrT2]	Distance of the shortest path [PrT3]	Toll [PrT4]
			minutes	minutes	km	yes/no
GP1	Arvier	Aosta	20	24	15	No
GP2	Avisè	Aosta	24	28	18	No
GP3	Aymavilles	Aosta	14	17	9	No
GP4	Cogne	Aosta	41	41	29	No
GP5	Introd	Aosta	23	27	16	No
GP6	Rhêmes-Notre-Dame	Aosta	42	45	32	No
GP7	Rhêmes-Saint-Georges	Aosta	34	38	25	No
GP8	Saint-Nicolas	Aosta	27	30	18	No
GP9	Valgrisenche	Aosta	41	44	30	No
GP10	Valsavarenche	Aosta	41	43	30	No

Table 11. Private transport accessibility indicators – Gran Paradis

Travel times vary from 14 minutes (Aymavilles – Aosta off-peak hours) to 45 minutes (Rhêmes-Notre-Dame – Aosta peak hours). The data shows that peak hours do not have a significant impact on travel times (max time difference between peak and off-peak hours equals 4 minutes). The distances span between 9 km (Aymavilles – Aosta) and 32 km (Rhêmes-Notre-Dame – Aosta). The increase of time corresponds to increase in distance between origins and destinations which confirms that the local traffic has little impact on travel times. None of the optimal routes for Gran Paradis includes paid

road sections. Figure 25 shows distribution of travel times and distances. Since the difference between peak and off-peak travel times is negligible the figure represents the average of both times.

Figure 25. Distribution of travel time and distance for private transport – Gran Paradis

Table 12 contains private transport accessibility indicators for Mont Cervin, organised in the same way as in the case of Gran Paradis.

Relation ID	Origin	Destination	Travel time on the shortest path (off-peak hours) on a weekday [PrT1]	Travel time on the shortest path (peak hours) on a weekday [PrT2]	Distance of the shortest path [PrT3]	Toll [PrT4]
			minutes	minutes	km	yes/no
MC1	Antey-Saint-André	Aosta	38	38	36	Yes
MC2	Antey-Saint-André	Saint-Vincent	16	16	13	No
MC3	Antey-Saint-André	Valtournenche	18	18	12	No
MC4	Antey-Saint-André	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	28	28	20	No
MC5	Antey-Saint-André	Châtillon	15	14	11	No
MC6	Antey-Saint-André	Verrès	24	24	23	Yes
MC7	Chambave	Aosta	26	27	19	No
MC8	Chambave	Saint-Vincent	12	11	8	No
MC9	Chambave	Valtournenche	31	30	23	No
MC10	Chambave	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	42	41	31	No
MC11	Chambave	Châtillon	10	9	6	No
MC12	Chambave	Verrès	20	19	19	Yes
MC13	Chambave-Arlier	Aosta	26	28	20	No
MC14	Chambave-Arlier	Saint-Vincent	13	13	10	No
MC15	Chambave-Arlier	Valtournenche	32	32	24	No
MC16	Chambave-Arlier	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	43	42	33	No
MC17	Chambave-Arlier	Châtillon	12	11	8	No
MC18	Chambave-Arlier	Verrès	21	21	20	Yes
MC19	Chamois	Aosta	Chamois is the only car-free Italian municipality (decided by local referendum in 1955) and cannot be accessed by this mean of transport. It can be reached by a cable car departing from Buisson or by foot.			
MC20	Chamois	Saint-Vincent				

MC21	Chamois	Valtournenche				
MC22	Chamois	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia				
MC23	Chamois	Châtillon				
MC24	Chamois	Verrès				
MC25	Châtillon	Aosta	29	30	28	Yes
MC26	Châtillon	Saint-Vincent	8	7	4	No
MC27	Châtillon	Valtournenche	25	25	18	No
MC28	Châtillon	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	36	35	27	No
MC29	Châtillon	Verrès	16	14	15	Yes
MC30	Châtillon Panorama	Aosta	27	28	27	Yes
MC31	Châtillon Panorama	Saint-Vincent	7	6	3	No
MC32	Châtillon Panorama	Valtournenche	25	25	18	No
MC33	Châtillon Panorama	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	36	35	27	No
MC34	Châtillon Panorama	Verrès	13	13	14	Yes
MC35	Châtillon Ussel	Aosta	32	32	30	Yes
MC36	Châtillon Ussel	Saint-Vincent	12	12	6	No
MC37	Châtillon Ussel	Valtournenche	34	33	23	No
MC38	Châtillon Ussel	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	45	44	31	No
MC39	Châtillon Ussel	Verrès	18	18	17	Yes
MC40	La Magdeleine	Aosta	50	49	43	Yes
MC41	La Magdeleine	Saint-Vincent	27	26	19	No
MC42	La Magdeleine	Valtournenche	28	28	18	No
MC43	La Magdeleine	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	39	39	27	No
MC44	La Magdeleine	Châtillon	26	25	17	No
MC45	La Magdeleine	Verrès	36	35	30	Yes
MC46	Pontey	Aosta	30	32	23	No
MC47	Pontey	Saint-Vincent	11	11	7	No
MC48	Pontey	Valtournenche	30	29	22	No
MC49	Pontey	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	41	40	30	No
MC50	Pontey	Châtillon	9	8	4	No
MC51	Pontey	Verrès	18	17	17	Yes
MC52	Saint-Denis	Aosta	31	33	23	No
MC53	Saint-Denis	Saint-Vincent	18	18	12	No
MC54	Saint-Denis	Valtournenche	37	36	27	No
MC55	Saint-Denis	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	47	47	35	No
MC56	Saint-Denis	Châtillon	16	16	10	No
MC57	Saint-Denis	Verrès	26	25	23	Yes
MC58	Saint-Vincent	Aosta	31	31	30	Yes
MC59	Saint-Vincent	Valtournenche	31	31	23	No
MC60	Saint-Vincent	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	42	41	31	No
M61	Saint-Vincent	Châtillon	9	8	4	No
M62	Saint-Vincent	Verrès	15	15	11	No

MC63	Saint-Vincent Moron	Aosta	35	34	31	Yes
MC64	Saint-Vincent Moron	Valtournenche	35	34	25	No
MC65	Saint-Vincent Moron	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	46	44	33	No
MC66	Saint-Vincent Moron	Châtillon	12	11	6	No
MC67	Saint-Vincent Moron	Verrès	21	19	18	Yes
MC68	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Aosta	33	32	30	Yes
MC69	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Valtournenche	33	32	23	No
MC70	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	44	43	32	No
MC71	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Châtillon	10	9	5	No
MC72	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Verrès	15	15	11	No
MC73	Torgnon	Aosta	46	45	41	Yes
MC74	Torgnon	Saint-Vincent	24	23	18	No
MC75	Torgnon	Valtournenche	24	24	16	No
MC76	Torgnon	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	35	34	25	No
MC77	Torgnon	Châtillon	22	21	16	No
MC78	Torgnon	Verrès	31	31	28	Yes
MC79	Verrayes	Aosta	32	33	23	No
MC80	Verrayes	Saint-Vincent	18	18	12	No
MC81	Verrayes	Valtournenche	37	37	27	No
MC82	Verrayes	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	48	47	35	No
MC83	Verrayes	Châtillon	17	17	10	No
MC84	Verrayes	Verrès	26	26	23	Yes
MC85	Verrayes Champagne	Aosta	23	24	17	No
MC86	Verrayes Champagne	Saint-Vincent	14	13	10	No
MC87	Verrayes Champagne	Valtournenche	32	32	25	No
MC88	Verrayes Champagne	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	43	42	33	No
MC89	Verrayes Champagne	Châtillon	12	11	8	No
MC90	Verrayes Champagne	Verrès	21	21	21	Yes

Table 12. Private transport accessibility indicators – Mont Cervin

Also, in this case the differences between peak and off-peak times are very small (max 2 minutes), which indicates that the additional peak traffic volume is too small to be significant. One of the municipalities (Chamois) is closed to car traffic and was excluded from analysis (see Table 12). Unlike in the case of Gran Paradis, certain OD relations require using toll roads for the optimal route choices. This happens in case of two destinations: Verrès and Aosta, which require taking the A5 highway for minimizing travel time. However, toll-free alternatives exist, without significant additional travel time (< 10 mins). Despite the distant location of some of the municipalities and mountainous access roads (e.g. La Magdeleine, Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia) most of the destinations have good accessibility and can be reached in relatively short time (see Figure 26). 59% of all destinations can be reached within an hour and only 5% of OD

combinations require time longer than 45 minutes, with maximum time of 50 minutes for La Magdeleine – Aosta. Most of the OD pairs require travelling relatively short distances (85% below 30 km).

Figure 26. Distribution of travel time and distance for private transport – Mont Cervin

Accessibility by public transport

Tables below summarize the public transport indicators for Gran Paradis (Table 13) and Mont Cervin (Table 14). For Gran Paradis the majority of considered municipalities have direct connections with the selected destination (Aosta). Valgrisenche and Valsavarenche are the most poorly connected municipalities requiring a transhipment in order to reach Aosta. Similar situation applies also to Rhêmes-Notre-Dame and Rhêmes-Saint-Georges, although in their case for the day of inquiry (14th June 2023) a single direct connection was found. Accessibility to the nearest public transport stop is generally good, with the walking distance never exceeding 1km neither for accessing the first PT stop nor for reaching the final destination from the last PT stop of the trip.

Relation ID	Origin	Destination	Minimum travel time on the shortest path on a weekday [PuT1]	Distance between the stops and the O / D [PuT2]	Transhipments on the shortest path on a weekday [PuT3]	Connections with 0 transhipment on a weekday [PuT4]	Connections with 1 transhipment on a weekday [PuT5]	Connections with 2-3 transhipments on a weekday [PuT6]	Connections in the 07-10 time slot taking the same time as the shortest path (+10 min) on a weekday [PuT7]	Connections in the 10-13 time slot taking the same time as the shortest path (+10 min) on a weekday [PuT8]
			minutes	meters	number	number	number	number	number	number
GP1	Arvier	Aosta	36	0.6 (0.0 + 0.6)	0	22	2	0	6	4
GP2	Avisé	Aosta	52	1.4 (0.8 + 0.6)	0	23	1	0	6	4
GP3	Aymavilles	Aosta	25	0.7 (0.1 + 0.6)	0	23	2	0	0	0
GP4	Cogne	Aosta	50	1.3 (0.8 + 0.5)	0	10	0	0	2	2
GP5	Introd	Aosta	38	0.5 (0 + 0.5)	0	7	10	0	1	0
GP6	Rhêmes-Notre-Dame	Aosta	70	0.6 (0.1 + 0.5)	0	1	2	0	0	0
GP7	Rhêmes-Saint-Georges	Aosta	66	1.3 (0.8 + 0.5)	0	1	2	0	0	0
GP8	Saint-Nicolas	Aosta	43	0.6 (0 + 0.6)	0	5	4	0	2	1
GP9	Valgrisenche	Aosta	77	0.7 (0.2 + 0.5)	1	0	3	0	0	0
GP10	Valsavarenche	Aosta	73	0.8 (0.3 + 0.5)	1	0	2	0	0	0

Table 13. Public transport accessibility indicators – Gran Paradis

Relation ID	Origin	Destination	Minimum travel time on the shortest path on a weekday [PuT1]	Distance between the stops and the O / D [PuT2]	Transhipments on the shortest path on a weekday [PuT3]	Connections with 0 transhipment on a weekday [PuT4]	Connections with 1 transhipment on a weekday [PuT5]	Connections with 2-3 transhipments on a weekday [PuT6]	Connections in the 07-10 time slot taking the same time as the shortest path (+10 min) on a weekday [PuT7]	Connections in the 10-13 time slot taking the same time as the shortest path (+10 min) on a weekday [PuT8]
			minutes	meters	number	number	number	number	number	number
MC1	Antey-Saint-André	Aosta	73	1.9 (1.4 + 0.5)	1	0	11	0	1	0
MC2	Antey-Saint-André	Saint-Vincent	43	1.9 (1.4 + 0.5)	0	1	10	0	1	0
MC3	Antey-Saint-André	Valtournenche	38	1.5 (1.4 + 0.1)	0	9	0	0	2	1
MC4	Antey-Saint-André	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	59	1.6 (1.4 + 0.2)	0	9	0	0	2	1
MC5	Antey-Saint-André	Châtillon	32	1.9 (1.4 + 0.5)	0	13	0	0	2	1
MC6	Antey-Saint-André	Verrès	63	1.8 (1.4 + 0.4)	1	0	11	0	1	0
MC7	Chambave	Aosta	39	0.5 (0 + 0.5)	1	22	9	0	5	4
MC8	Chambave	Saint-Vincent	25	1.0 (0.5 + 0.5)	0	22	1	1	5	4
MC9	Chambave	Valtournenche	54	0.6 (0.5 + 0.1)	1	0	7	0	1	1
MC10	Chambave	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	75	0.7 (0.5 + 0.2)	1	0	7	0	1	1
MC11	Chambave	Châtillon	13	0.5 (0 + 0.5)	0	27	0	1	5	4
MC12	Chambave	Verrès	40	0.9 (0.5 + 0.4)	0	21	7	0	5	4
MC13	Chambave-Arlier	Aosta	36	0.5 (0 + 0.5)	1	22	9	0	0	0
MC14	Chambave-Arlier	Saint-Vincent	32	1.6 (1.1 + 0.5)	0	23	1	0	4	5
MC15	Chambave-Arlier	Valtournenche	61	1.2 (1.1 + 0.1)	1	0	7	0	1	1
MC16	Chambave-Arlier	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	82	1.3 (1.1 + 0.2)	1	0	7	0	1	1
MC17	Chambave-Arlier	Châtillon	22	0.5 (0 + 0.5)	1	28	1	0	4	5
MC18	Chambave-Arlier	Verrès	47	1.5 (1.1 + 0.4)	0	22	4	1	4	4

MC19	Chamois	Aosta	No conventional public transport available. Chamois can be reached by a cable car departing from Buisson or by foot.							
MC20	Chamois	Saint-Vincent								
MC21	Chamois	Valtournenche								
MC22	Chamois	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia								
MC23	Chamois	Châtillon								
MC24	Chamois	Verrès								
MC25	Châtillon	Aosta	43	1.9 (1.4 + 0.5)	0	41	0	0	9	7
MC26	Châtillon	Saint-Vincent	19	1.0 (0.5 + 0.5)	0	48	0	0	11	8
MC27	Châtillon	Valtournenche	38	0.6 (0.5 + 0.1)	0	9	0	0	1	1
MC28	Châtillon	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	60	0.7 (0.5 + 0.2)	0	9	0	0	1	1
MC29	Châtillon	Verrès	33	0.9 (0.5 + 0.4)	0	41	0	0	8	8
MC30	Châtillon Panorama	Aosta	41	1.7 (1.2 + 0.5)	0	41	0	0	9	7
MC31	Châtillon Panorama	Saint-Vincent	17	0.9 (0.4 + 0.5)	0	48	0	0	11	8
MC32	Châtillon Panorama	Valtournenche	41	0.5 (0.4 + 0.1)	0	9	0	0	1	1
MC33	Châtillon Panorama	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	62	0.6 (0.4 + 0.2)	0	9	0	0	1	1
MC34	Châtillon Panorama	Verrès	31	0.8 (0.4 + 0.4)	0	41	0	0	9	8
MC35	Châtillon Ussel	Aosta	61	3.4 (2.9 + 0.5)	0	19	4	0	3	3
MC36	Châtillon Ussel	Saint-Vincent	47	3.4 (2.9 + 0.5)	0	23	0	0	5	4
MC37	Châtillon Ussel	Valtournenche	75	3.0 (2.9 + 0.1)	0	7	0	0	1	1
MC38	Châtillon Ussel	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	97	3.1 (2.9 + 0.2)	0	7	0	0	1	1
MC39	Châtillon Ussel	Verrès	61	4.1 (2.9 + 1.2)	0	19	2	0	4	4
MC40	La Magdeleine	Aosta	The municipality is not accessible by public transport. The nearest bus stop can be accessed in Antey-Saint-André, located 11 km from la Magdeleine							
MC41	La Magdeleine	Saint-Vincent								
MC42	La Magdeleine	Valtournenche								
MC43	La Magdeleine	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia								
MC44	La Magdeleine	Châtillon								
MC45	La Magdeleine	Verrès								

MC46	Pontey	Aosta	41	0.7 (0.2 + 0.5)	1	20	14	0	0	0
MC47	Pontey	Saint-Vincent	28	0.7 (0.2 + 0.5)	0	32	1	0	5	2
MC48	Pontey	Valtournenche	61	0.3 (0.2 + 0.1)	1	0	6	0	1	0
MC49	Pontey	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	82	0.4 (0.2 + 0.2)	1	0	6	0	1	0
MC50	Pontey	Châtillon	22	0.7 (0.2 + 0.5)	0	35	1	0	5	2
MC51	Pontey	Verrès	44	1.4 (0.2 + 1.2)	1	15	13	0	1	0
MC52	Saint-Denis	Aosta	70	0.7 (0.1 + 0.6)	1	0	4	1	0	0
MC53	Saint-Denis	Saint-Vincent	39	0.6 (0.1 + 0.5)	1	1	4	0	0	0
MC54	Saint-Denis	Valtournenche	94	0.2 (0.1 + 0.1)	1	0	3	0	0	1
MC55	Saint-Denis	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	115	0.3 (0.1 + 0.2)	1	0	3	0	0	1
MC56	Saint-Denis	Châtillon	23	0.6 (0.1 + 0.5)	0	5	0	0	0	0
MC57	Saint-Denis	Verrès	55	0.5 (0.1 + 0.4)	1	0	4	1	0	0
MC58	Saint-Vincent	Aosta	55	1.1 (0.5 + 0.6)	0	21	18	0	9	6
MC59	Saint-Vincent	Valtournenche	49	0.6 (0.5 + 0.1)	0	2	6	0	0	0
MC60	Saint-Vincent	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	70	0.7 (0.5 + 0.2)	0	2	6	0	0	0
M61	Saint-Vincent	Châtillon	20	1.0 (0.5 + 0.5)	0	47	0	0	11	7
M62	Saint-Vincent	Verrès	29	0.9 (0.5 + 0.4)	0	22	3	0	6	4
MC63	Saint-Vincent Moron	Aosta	79	3.1 (2.5 + 0.6)	0	21	14	0	5	4
MC64	Saint-Vincent Moron	Valtournenche	83	2.6 (2.5 + 0.1)	1	0	5	0	1	0
MC65	Saint-Vincent Moron	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	104	2.7 (2.5 + 0.2)	1	0	5	0	1	0
MC66	Saint-Vincent Moron	Châtillon	44	3.0 (2.5 + 0.5)	0	42	0	0	9	8
MC67	Saint-Vincent Moron	Verrès	49	2.8 (2.4 + 0.4)	0	23	7	0	5	4
MC68	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Aosta	59	1.5 (0.9 + 0.6)	0	21	17	0	8	6
MC69	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Valtournenche	61	0.2 (0.1 + 0.1)	1	0	8	0	1	0
MC70	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	82	0.3 (0.1 + 0.2)	1	0	8	0	1	0
MC71	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Châtillon	22	0.6 (0.1 + 0.5)	0	45	0	0	11	7
MC72	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Verrès	30	1.3 (0.9 + 0.4)	0	22	4	0	6	4

MC73	Torgnon	Aosta	76	0.8 (0.3 + 0.5)	1	0	3	1	0	0
MC74	Torgnon	Saint-Vincent	52	0.8 (0.3 + 0.5)	1	0	3	1	0	0
MC75	Torgnon	Valtournenche	40	0.3 (0.2 + 0.1)	0	1	4	0	1	0
MC76	Torgnon	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	61	0.4 (0.2 + 0.2)	0	1	4	0	1	0
MC77	Torgnon	Châtillon	35	0.8 (0.3 + 0.5)	0	5	1	0	0	0
MC78	Torgnon	Verrès	67	0.7 (0.3 + 0.4)	1	0	3	1	0	0
MC79	Verrayes	Aosta	70	0.8 (0.2 + 0.6)	1	0	5	1	0	0
MC80	Verrayes	Saint-Vincent	39	0.7 (0.2 + 0.5)	1	1	4	0	0	0
MC81	Verrayes	Valtournenche	94	0.3 (0.2 + 0.1)	1	0	3	0	0	1
MC82	Verrayes	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	115	0.4 (0.2 + 0.2)	1	0	3	0	0	1
MC83	Verrayes	Châtillon	23	0.7 (0.2 + 0.5)	0	5	0	0	0	0
MC84	Verrayes	Verrès	55	0.6 (0.2 + 0.4)	1	0	4	1	0	0
MC85	Verrayes Champagne	Aosta	36	0.9 (0.3 + 0.6)	0	22	3	0	5	4
MC86	Verrayes Champagne	Saint-Vincent	26	0.8 (0.3 + 0.5)	0	22	1	1	5	4
MC87	Verrayes Champagne	Valtournenche	55	0.4 (0.3 + 0.1)	1	0	7	0	1	1
MC88	Verrayes Champagne	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	76	0.5 (0.3 + 0.2)	1	0	7	0	1	1
MC89	Verrayes Champagne	Châtillon	17	0.8 (0.3 + 0.5)	0	26	0	1	5	4
MC90	Verrayes Champagne	Verrès	41	0.7 (0.3 + 0.4)	0	21	5	0	5	4

Table 14. Public transport accessibility indicators – Mont Cervin

No location was found for which the best available solution would require more than one transshipment. Considering this indicator, the best connected origins are Châtillon, Châtillon Panorama, Châtillon Ussel and Saint-Vincent, for which it is possible to reach each destination without transshipment. On the other hand, Verrayes and Saint-Denis are among the worst connected municipalities. Some of the origins are poorly connected to the nearest public transport stop and a travel requires relatively long initial walking distance, in particular Châtillon Ussel, Saint-Vincent Moron, and Antey-Saint-André.

Comparisons of private and public transport performances

The tables below represent the reduction of travel times when using a car for all OD pairs in comparison to travel times of public transport.

Relation ID	Origin	Destination	Minimum travel time PT [PuT1]	Average travel time car	Car travel time reduction	Car travel time reduction
			minutes	minutes	minutes	%
GP1	Arvier	Aosta	36	22	14	39%
GP2	Avise	Aosta	52	26	26	50%
GP3	Aymavilles	Aosta	25	16	9	37%
GP4	Cogne	Aosta	50	41	9	18%
GP5	Introd	Aosta	38	25	13	35%
GP6	Rhêmes-Notre-Dame	Aosta	70	44	26	38%
GP7	Rhêmes-Saint-Georges	Aosta	66	36	30	45%
GP8	Saint-Nicolas	Aosta	43	29	14	33%
GP9	Valgrisenche	Aosta	77	43	35	45%
GP10	Valsavarenche	Aosta	73	42	31	43%

Table 15. Gran Paradis: private transport – public transport times comparison.

The highest difference in time in absolute terms can be seen for Valgrisenche, Valsavarenche, and Rhêmes-Saint-Georges, which is in line with the results of preceding analysis showing that these are the locations with the worst public transport service. In relative terms, the highest possible time reduction was observed for Avise, for which it is possible to reduce the travel time by half. Despite many direct public transport connections during the day it might be a factor attracting the local citizens towards the car.

Relation ID	Origin	Destination	Minimum travel time PT [PuT1]	Average travel time car	Car travel time reduction	Car travel time reduction
			minutes	minutes	minutes	%
MC1	Antey-Saint-André	Aosta	73	38	35	48%
MC2	Antey-Saint-André	Saint-Vincent	43	16	27	63%
MC3	Antey-Saint-André	Valtournenche	38	18	20	52%
MC4	Antey-Saint-André	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	59	28	31	52%
MC5	Antey-Saint-André	Châtillon	32	15	18	55%
MC6	Antey-Saint-André	Verrès	63	24	39	62%
				Average:	28	55%
MC7	Chambave	Aosta	39	27	13	32%
MC8	Chambave	Saint-Vincent	25	12	13	53%
MC9	Chambave	Valtournenche	54	31	24	44%

MC10	Chambave	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	75	42	34	45%
MC11	Chambave	Châtillon	13	10	4	28%
MC12	Chambave	Verrès	40	20	21	51%
				Average:	18	42%
MC13	Chambave-Arlier	Aosta	36	27	9	25%
MC14	Chambave-Arlier	Saint-Vincent	32	13	19	59%
MC15	Chambave-Arlier	Valtournenche	61	32	29	48%
MC16	Chambave-Arlier	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	82	42,5	40	48%
MC17	Chambave-Arlier	Châtillon	22	11,5	11	48%
MC18	Chambave-Arlier	Verrès	47	21	26	56%
				Average:	22	47%
MC25	Châtillon	Aosta	43	29,5	13	31%
MC26	Châtillon	Saint-Vincent	19	7,5	11	60%
MC27	Châtillon	Valtournenche	38	25	13	35%
MC28	Châtillon	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	60	35,5	25	41%
MC29	Châtillon	Verrès	33	15	18	55%
				Average:	16	44%
MC30	Châtillon Panorama	Aosta	41	27,5	13	33%
MC31	Châtillon Panorama	Saint-Vincent	17	6,5	10	61%
MC32	Châtillon Panorama	Valtournenche	41	25	16	39%
MC33	Châtillon Panorama	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	62	35,5	27	43%
MC34	Châtillon Panorama	Verrès	31	13	18	58%
				Average:	17	46%
MC35	Châtillon Ussel	Aosta	61	32	29	48%
MC36	Châtillon Ussel	Saint-Vincent	47	12	35	74%
MC37	Châtillon Ussel	Valtournenche	75	33,5	42	55%
MC38	Châtillon Ussel	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	97	44,5	52	54%
MC39	Châtillon Ussel	Verrès	61	18	43	71%
				Average:	36	58%
MC46	Pontey	Aosta	41	31	10	25%
MC47	Pontey	Saint-Vincent	28	11	17	60%
MC48	Pontey	Valtournenche	61	29,5	32	52%
MC49	Pontey	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	82	40,5	42	51%
MC50	Pontey	Châtillon	22	8,5	14	62%
MC51	Pontey	Verrès	44	17,5	27	61%
				Average:	24	52%
MC52	Saint-Denis	Aosta	70	32	38	54%
MC53	Saint-Denis	Saint-Vincent	39	18	21	54%
MC54	Saint-Denis	Valtournenche	94	36,5	57	61%
MC55	Saint-Denis	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	115	47	68	59%
MC56	Saint-Denis	Châtillon	23	16	7	32%
MC57	Saint-Denis	Verrès	55	25,5	30	54%
				Average:	37	52%

MC58	Saint-Vincent	Aosta	55	31	24	44%
MC59	Saint-Vincent	Valtournenche	49	31	18	36%
MC60	Saint-Vincent	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	70	41,5	29	41%
M61	Saint-Vincent	Châtillon	20	8,5	11	57%
M62	Saint-Vincent	Verrès	29	15	14	49%
				Average:	22	47%
MC63	Saint-Vincent Moron	Aosta	79	34,5	45	56%
MC64	Saint-Vincent Moron	Valtournenche	83	34,5	48	58%
MC65	Saint-Vincent Moron	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	104	45	59	57%
MC66	Saint-Vincent Moron	Châtillon	44	11,5	32	74%
MC67	Saint-Vincent Moron	Verrès	49	20	29	59%
				Average:	39	59%
MC68	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Aosta	59	32,5	27	45%
MC69	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Valtournenche	61	32,5	28	46%
MC70	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	82	43,5	38	47%
MC71	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Châtillon	22	9,5	12	56%
MC72	Saint-Vincent Cillian	Verrès	30	15	15	50%
				Average:	27	50%
MC73	Torgnon	Aosta	76	45,5	31	40%
MC74	Torgnon	Saint-Vincent	52	23,5	28	54%
MC75	Torgnon	Valtournenche	40	24	16	40%
MC76	Torgnon	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	61	34,5	27	44%
MC77	Torgnon	Châtillon	35	21,5	14	39%
MC78	Torgnon	Verrès	67	31	36	54%
				Average:	25	45%
MC79	Verrayes	Aosta	70	32,5	37	53%
MC80	Verrayes	Saint-Vincent	39	18	21	54%
MC81	Verrayes	Valtournenche	94	37	57	60%
MC82	Verrayes	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	115	47,5	67	59%
MC83	Verrayes	Châtillon	23	17	6	27%
MC84	Verrayes	Verrès	55	26	29	53%
				Average:	36	51%
MC85	Verrayes Champagne	Aosta	36	23,5	13	35%
MC86	Verrayes Champagne	Saint-Vincent	26	13,5	12	48%
MC87	Verrayes Champagne	Valtournenche	55	32	23	42%
MC88	Verrayes Champagne	Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia	76	42,5	34	44%
MC89	Verrayes Champagne	Châtillon	17	11,5	5	32%
MC90	Verrayes Champagne	Verrès	41	21	20	49%
				Average:	18	42%

Table 16. Mont Cervin: private transport – public transport times comparison.

For Mont Cervin Aosta is the destination for which using the car instead of public transport seems to bring the least benefit in terms of travel time (average improvement of 41%), whereas using private transport is most beneficial for

Saint-Vincent and Verrès (58% and 56% respectively). The origins for which using a car brings the most travel time advantage are Saint-Vincent Moron (average reduction of 59%) and Châtillon Ussel (58%). As already indicated, it is most probably due to the large distance to the nearest bus stop which has large impact on total travel time.

The maps below show graphical comparison of the average times of private transport and the shortest time for public transport for various origins and destinations.

Mont Cervin – destination: Aosta

Mont Cervin – destination: Châtillon

Mont Cervin – destination: Saint-Vincent

Mont Cervin – destination: Valtournenche

Mont Cervin – destination: Valtournenche Breuil-Cervinia

Mont Cervin – destination: Verrès

